

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Exponential-algebraic optimal quadrature formulas in a Hilber space

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Introduction and statement of the problem

In the present work we consider a quadrature formula of the following form

$$\int_0^1 f(x)dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}f(x_\beta) + \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1}(f'(x_\beta) + f(x_\beta)), \quad (1)$$

where $C_{\beta,0}$, $C_{\beta,1}$ are coefficients, $x_\beta = h\beta$ are nodes and $h = 1/N$, N is a natural number, an integrand f belongs to the Hilbert space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ of functions that are square integrable with second derivative [1,2]. The space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ is equipped by the norm

$$\|f\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}} = \sqrt{\int_0^1 (f'(x) + f(x))dx}.$$

We note that in (1) the coefficients $C_{\beta,0}$ are known and have the form

$$C_{0,0} = \frac{e^h - 1}{e^h + 1}, \quad C_{\beta,0} = \frac{2(e^h - 1)}{e^h + 1}, \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1, \quad \text{and} \quad C_{N,0} = \frac{e^h - 1}{e^h + 1}. \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, they are coefficients of the optimal quadrature formula of the form

$$\int_0^1 f(x)dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}f(x_\beta)$$

in the space $W_2^{(1,0)}$ [2].

Then we have possiblity to minimize the error of the formula (1) by the coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$. It should be noted that the following difference is called *the error* of the quadrature formula (1)

$$(\ell, f) = \int_0^1 f(x)dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}f(x_\beta) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1}(f'(x_\beta) + f(x_\beta)). \quad (3)$$

This difference defines a linear functional ℓ acting to the function f as

$$(\ell, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(x)f(x)dx$$

and ℓ is called *the error functional* of the quadrature formula (1) and is expressed by the following expression

$$\ell(x) = \varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}\delta(x - x_{\beta}) + \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1}(\delta'(x - x_{\beta}) - \delta(x - x_{\beta})), \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon_{[0,1]}(x)$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[0, 1]$, $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta-function.

It is known that the norm of the error functional ℓ is expressed as

$$\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)*}} = \sup_{f, \|f\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}} \neq 0} \frac{|(\ell, f)|}{\|f\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}}.$$

From here, we get the following upper estimate for the absolute value of the error of the quadrature formulas (1)

$$|(\ell, f)| \leq \|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)*}} \cdot \|f\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}. \quad (5)$$

Hence, taking into account the definition of the norm of the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$, it is easy to see that the error of the quadrature formula (1) is zero for the functions $f(x) = e^{-x}$ and $f(x) = 1$. That is the quadrature formula (1) is exact for any linear combination of the functions $f(x) = e^{-x}$ and $f(x) = 1$ and we have the following equations

$$(\ell, e^{-x}) = 0 \text{ and } (\ell, 1) = 0. \quad (6)$$

One can easily check that the first equation from (6) is satisfied due to coefficients $C_{\beta,0}$, $\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$, given by (2). Indeed, taking into account (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\ell, e^{-x}) &= \int_0^1 e^{-x} dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}e^{-x_{\beta}} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1}(-e^{-x_{\beta}} + e^{-x_{\beta}}) \\ &= \int_0^1 e^{-x} dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0}e^{-x_{\beta}} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Then from the second equation of (6) we get the existence condition of the quadrature formula of the form (1) in the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$. Thus for the coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ of the quadrature formula (1) we have the following

$$\begin{aligned} (\ell, 1) &= \int_0^1 1 dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} \cdot 1 - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1}(0 + 1) = \\ &= 1 - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, using (2), for the coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ we get

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} = 1 - \frac{2(e^h - 1)}{h(e^h + 1)}. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, for existence of a quadrature formula of the form (1) it is needed satisfying the condition $N \geq 1$. Furthermore, a quadrature formula of the form (1) that satisfies the conditions (6) we call *an exponential-algebraic quadrature formula with derivative* in the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$.

Among quadrature formulas of the form (1) with given coefficients $C_{\beta,0}$ in the Hilbert space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ *an optimal one* is a quadrature formula of the form (1) with coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ that give the absolute minimum value to the norm $\|\ell\|$ of the error functional (4). The coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ that give this minimum are called *the optimal coefficients* and corresponding quadrature formula of the form (1) we call *the exponential-algebraic optimal quadrature formula* of the form (1) in the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$.

Thus, to get the optimal quadrature formula of the form (1) we should solve the following problems.

Problem 1. Find an upper bound for the error of the quadrature formula (1) in the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$, that is, calculate the norm $\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}$ of the error functional (4).

We note that the norm of the error functional (4) becomes a multivariable function with respect to coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$, $\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$. In order to get an optimal quadrature formula it is natural to solve the following problem.

Problem 2. Find coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ that give the minimum to the norm $\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}$ of the error functional ℓ .

Thus, solving Problems 1 and 2 successively we get an optimal quadrature formula of the form (1). Here we present solution of Problems 1 and 2. Therefore, the aim of the paper is to solve Problems 1 and 2.

For this, in the next sections, we calculate the norm $\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}$ of the error functional ℓ and get the coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ that give the minimum to this norm.

An extremal function of the quadrature formula(1)

In the present section we find an extremal function for the quadrature formula (1). Then, in the next section, using the obtained extremal function we get the norm of the error functional (4) that allows us to obtain the sharp upper bound for the error of the quadrature formula (1).

It should be noted that the definition of an extremal function of a cubature formula with corresponding error functional on a Banach space was given by S.L.Sobolev (see, for example, [3]). The extremal function allows us to get a sharp upper bound for the error of the cubature formula.

Here, to estimate the error of the quadrature formula (1) on functions of the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ we use the Riesz representation theorem about general form of a linear continuous functional on Hilbert spaces and apply the definition of the extremal function of the quadrature formula (1).

By the definition (see, for instance, [1]) for any linear continuous functional (in particular, for the error functional (4)), defined on the Hilbert space $W_2^{(2,1)}$, an extremal function ψ_ℓ satisfies the following equality

$$(\ell, \psi_\ell) = \|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)*}} \|\psi_\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}. \quad (8)$$

Based on the Riesz theorem the following equality holds

$$\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)*}} = \|\psi_\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}} \quad (9)$$

and from the last two equations we have

$$\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)*}}^2 = (\ell, \psi_\ell). \quad (10)$$

In the Hilbert space $W_2^{(2,1)}(0, 1)$ the extremal function that satisfies equalities (8) and (9) has the following representation (see, for example, [1])

$$\psi_\ell(x) = \ell(x) * G_2(x) + p_0 + de^{-x}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$G_2(x) = \frac{\text{sign}x}{2} \left(\frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{2} - x \right), \quad (12)$$

p_0 and d are constants.

For the extremal function we have the following result.

Theorem 1. *The extremal function (11) of the quadrature formula (1) in the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ has the following analytic representation*

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_\ell(x) = & \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} \left(\frac{\text{sign}(x - x_\beta)}{2} (e^{-(x-x_\beta)} + x - x_\beta - 1) \right) - \\ & - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} G_2(x - x_\beta) + \int_0^1 G_2(x - y) dy + p_0 + de^{-x}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $G_2(x)$ is defined by (12).

Proof. Indeed, calculating the convolution in (11) we get (13). Let us do it. By the definition of the convolution for continuous variable functions for the convolution $(\ell * G_2)(x)$ we have

$$(\ell * G_2)(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(y) G_2(x - y) dy.$$

Hence, using (4), we get

$$(\ell * G_2)(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\varepsilon_{[0,1]}(y) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} \delta(y - x_\beta) + \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} (\delta'(y - x_\beta) - \delta(x - x_\beta)) \right) G_2(x - y) dy.$$

Then, using properties

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x - a) f(x) dx = f(a) \text{ and } \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta'(x - a) f(x) dx = -f'(a)$$

of the Dirac delta-function, for the last expression we have

$$(\ell * G_2)(x) = \int_0^1 G_2(x - y) dy - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} G_2(x - x_\beta) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} \left((G_2(x - y))'_{y=x_\beta} + G_2(x - x_\beta) \right). \quad (14)$$

Now, using the well known formula $(\text{sign}(x))' = 2\delta(x)$, we have

$$(G_2(x - y))'_{y=x_\beta} = -\frac{\text{sign}(x - x_\beta)}{2} \left(\frac{e^{x-x_\beta} + e^{-(x-x_\beta)}}{2} - 1 \right).$$

Putting the last expression into (14) and taking into account (12) for the convolution we come

$$(\ell * G_2)(x) = \int_0^1 G_2(x - y) dy - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} G_2(x - x_\beta) - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} \left(\frac{\text{sign}(x - x_\beta)}{2} \left(-\frac{e^{x-x_\beta} + e^{-(x-x_\beta)}}{2} + 1 + \frac{e^{x-x_\beta} - e^{-(x-x_\beta)}}{2} - (x - x_\beta) \right) \right).$$

Simplifying the last expression and putting it into (11) we get (13).

Theorem 1 is proved.

An upper bound for the error of the quadrature formula (1)

Now we are ready to calculate the norm of the error functional (4) that gives us an upper bound for the error of the quadrature formula (1). Using Theorem 1 and (4), from (10) by direct calculation we have the following main result which is the solution of Problem 1.

Theorem 2. *The norm of the error functional (4) for quadrature formulas of the form (1) is expressed as follows*

$$\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(2,1)}}^2 = \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\beta,1} C_{\gamma,1} \frac{|x_\beta - x_\gamma|}{2} + 2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,1} \left(\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma,0} \frac{\text{sign}(x_\beta - x_\gamma)}{2} (e^{-(x_\gamma - x_\beta)} + \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +x_\gamma - x_\beta - 1) + \int_0^1 \frac{\text{sign}(x - x_\beta)}{2} (e^{-(x-x_\beta)} + x - x_\beta - 1) dx) + \\
& + \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta,0} \left(\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma,0} G_2(x_\beta - x_\gamma) - 2 \int_0^1 G_2(x - x_\beta) dx \right) + \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G_2(x - y) dx dy. \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

Next we consider the problem of minimization of the norm (15) with respect to coefficients $C_{\beta,1}$ under the condition (7).

The coefficients of the optimal quadrature formula (1)

In this section we give the main result of the paper. We present the coefficients of the optimal quadrature formula (1). In order to get the optimal coefficients we use the Lagrange method of undetermined multipliers.

We consider the following Lagrange function for minimization of the expression (15) under the condition (7)

$$\Lambda(C_{\beta,1}, \lambda) = \|\ell\|^2 - 2\lambda(\ell, 1).$$

For the critical point of the last function we get the system

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma,1} \frac{|h\beta - h\gamma|}{2} + \lambda = F \cdot \left((h\beta)^2 + (h\beta) - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N, \\
& \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\gamma,1} = -2F,
\end{aligned}$$

where $F = \frac{e^h - 1}{h(e^h + 1)} - \frac{1}{2}$.

It should be noted that the solution of the last system gives the minimum to the norm (15) under the condition (7).

The following is true.

Theorem 3. *In the space $W_2^{(2,1)}$ the coefficients of the optimal quadrature formula (1) have the following representations*

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{0,0} &= \frac{e^h - 1}{e^h + 1}, \\
C_{\beta,0} &= \frac{2(e^h - 1)}{e^h + 1}, \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1, \\
C_{N,0} &= \frac{e^h - 1}{e^h + 1}, \\
C_{0,1} &= hF, \\
C_{\beta,1} &= 2hF, \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1, \\
C_{N,1} &= (h - 4)F,
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$F = \frac{e^h - 1}{h(e^h + 1)} - \frac{1}{2}.$$

Thus, we have solved Problem 2.

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